

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: RANI****FIRST NAME: NEHA****PROGRAM CODE: MIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (Plagiarism – 5%)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 2013 on Windows 10

List your seven key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay Writing Essentials (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-13)
3. Literature review (EUCLID 2019, 17-23)
4. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 24)
5. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
6. Chicago Style and Usage (EUCLID 2019, 44)
7. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (EUCLID 2019, 56-59)

UNPACKING THE ATTRIBUTES OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

An academic essay informs readers of a point of view using facts. It should respond to the issue and counterargument as the majority of essays offer a prompt. In obedience to Raewyn Conell, "Research is something that everyone can do, and everyone ought to do. It is simply collecting information and thinking systematically about it" (D'Cruz and Jones 2004, 5). A student can expect to write a research, narrative, expository, informative or, persuasive essay—each of these needs a different approach. However, in my situation, I need to analyze or assess the subject and provide evidence-based arguments. Evidence can either be absolute, demonstrative, documentary or, testimonial. I have lately done a lot of research regarding what makes a good writing piece and how poor writing leads to good writing. Before I started, I took some time to thoroughly review my ACA-401 period one coursepack followed by a powerful video presentation. I consider this a goal, which encouraged me to ponder such issues as to why and how I decided to write this, providing facts and arguments. I attempt to write summaries on essential aspects of essay writing, plagiarism, citation style that includes Chicago style and usage.

2) **ESSAY WRITING**

When I was going through this coursepack, the first aspect to consider was, "What are the standards for writing an effective essay? I agree with what Robert A Day quoted, "Writing of an accurate, understandable, paper is just as important as the research itself" (Wallwork 2016, 4). I realized that understanding the topic is the most critical move in writing an essay. An essay should begin with a thesis statement or argument that will direct the rest of it. A thesis argument should be brief and should discuss all critical points in the essay.

a) Phases of Essay Writing

If I think about the reason behind composing an essay, I would be more inspired to write it well. It is instead vital for me to concentrate on the planning stage. Firstly, I should figure out how many paragraphs I would like to draft my essay. After that, I should list facts for the essay and compose a short explanation of using them in the arguments or statements. It might seem to be extra work, but it would help me a lot to avoid procrastination. Therefore, I should do the analysis, researched the topic and, formulated an initial plan.

b) Researching the Topic

An essay should have proof that supports the position up to an extent complemented with own thoughts. Alternatively, I can show evidence that invalidates the stance and content against that evidence to reinforce the position.

i) Writing the Essay

I took the plunge by creating a concise draft based on my previous research with a blueprint, progressing from general to specific. I aimed to create consistency of discussion and decided whether my research was well conducted and had a clear framework. An essay consists of three parts: an introduction, a body and, a conclusion.

An introduction serves as a guide for the essay that establishes the framework and purpose. It should grab the attention of the reader. I also used some quotes and examples to make it more meaningful.

Although a body is the second part of the essay, I wrote it before the introduction to avoid getting lost. It encouraged me to thoroughly form my thoughts and suggestions before returning to the critical points' opening and integration. The essay's body should provide a paragraph that addresses the question by establishing the debate, presenting facts to support the arguments, and explaining my research and experience during the topic's study.

The conclusion always turns from specific to general. I stated the response and recapitulated the essay without adding new material to the decision.

ii) Referencing and Revision of the Essay

It is essential to include the referees. I should appreciate the efforts of researchers and writers by citing them. Also, I read the paper many times. Even on the second read, I could point out some content and mechanical errors that would improve the paper's quality by eliminating them.

3) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is the utilization of a person's insights and knowledge without appreciating the source. Plagiarism comprises paraphrasing without attribution. As long as I correctly cite my references, paraphrasing is not plagiarism. As Jacob Braude quoted, "All work and no plagiarism makes a dull speech" (Esar 1995, 601). However, I will also agree with this cite, "If you steal from one author, it's plagiarism. If you steal from many, it's research" (*Saturday Review* 1952, 14). So, in my opinion, looking at someone else's work is beneficial in terms of generating new ideas, seeking encouragement and incorporating something different into my work. To distinguish between copying and seeking encouragement and ideas, I should use citation in my writing work. I learned that there are two aspects for quotation.

a) In-Text Citations

It is the reference that is present in the body of the text. It gives information about the source, including the author's name and the parenthesis source's page number.

b) List of Works Cited

List of references or the Bibliography at the end of the document. It provides information about the publication of each source cited (EUCLID 2019, 10).

4) GUIDELINES FOR PAPER WRITING

This section aims to describe a primary hypothesis around which substantiated concepts enable me to stay focused by critically testing theories that revolve around the subject to discuss. I should not generalize the inference, write concise sentences, abstain from dull and confusing topics, avoid plagiarism, and back up assertions.

5) CITATION STYLE

Chapter 5 of the coursepack concludes that a citation style specifies the detail used in a citation and presents the format and punctuation components and another formatting. There are different methods for citing the resources. The citation form used can vary depending upon the academic field, such as APA (American Psychological Association), MLA (Modern Language Association), CMS (Chicago Manuals of Styles),/Turabian. EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian), but other internationally recognized rules are acceptable (EUCLID 2019). The Turabian style named after Kate Larimore Turabian specifies spelling, formatting, and citing the references. This style combines syntax and sentence structure guidelines that are popular in American English. In general, the Turabian style has two simple references framework:

1. Notes (footnotes and endnotes) and Bibliography
2. Author-date

Selecting between the two is often determined by the research topic and the context of the references quoted. Furthermore, Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck suggests using Zotero in the first video of my course. Zotero has the perfect platform for labeling and adding comments to my citations. Zotero has thousands of citation forms that are conveniently customizable. Following pre-installed options, I saw several other styles. If I need any specific style, I click "get additional styles" to search for the desired style.

6) LATIN INFLUENCE IN WRITING

Journals related to health and medicine often use the Latin language. The majority of anatomical terminologies (femur, homo, and so on) are Latin in nature. Apart from that, I used many popular Latin abbreviations and phrases (*e.g.*, and, *i.e.*). The section gives me a complete list of Latin abbreviations that I can use in my writing.

7) GLITCHES AND HIGHLIGHTS

a) English- A Vague Language?

"The English language is an arsenal of weapons. If you are going to brandish them without checking to see whether or not they are loaded, you must expect to have them explode in your face time to time" (Fry 2010, 66). This quote is suitable because I studied British English in my school or at least a translation. Being an Indian, my English is more traditional and primitive than modern British English. My accent is often more informal since I sound as if I am writing, which is not the case for native speakers. Besides, more American words have entered the language of non-native speakers like me due to expanded exposure to American media such as novels, TV shows, movies, social media, etc. Non-

native speakers, most people who speak, read, and write English formally or regularly, have a combination of British and American dialects. Learning English was simple at first, but after I mastered the fundamentals, the language became increasingly puzzling, which is also a composite of eight languages.

Consequently, we have a language with lots of rules and lots of limitations. Not just that, but many of the rules are in direct opposition to one another. Most English words derive from other languages, so they do not obey the rules but are still a part of the Vocabulary. The prominence of English in global research has recently become a topic of discussion in the media. As a result, writing academic research papers has become more and more relevant.

On the other hand, students often have writing issues in conceptual arguments, ethnic intervention, contextual arrangement, textual reference, assertion form, grammatical law, and many more. In my opinion, the most prevalent challenge to individuals reported in writing is asserting knowledge. EUCLID recommends Grammarly to identify possible problems in the text automatically and include context-specific advice for syntax, pronunciation, spelling mistakes correction, tone, punctuation, and even plagiarism. I agree with EUCLID and applaud their initiative because it saves a lot of time and effort. Why should I devote too much time to learn the differences between British and American English and their complex rules? Is there any correlation between research performance and English language proficiency training? Instead, we can use Grammarly to verify and correct our grammatical errors. Furthermore, I assume that language is only a way to communicate and only be regarded as a skill rather than a means of assessing one's intellect and knowledge.

b) Accessibility to Hyperlinks

"Not wishing to inundate you with links" (EUCLID 2019, 26), "the Economic style guide is freely available" (EUCLID 2019, 25). I would suggest using hyperlinks for vital topics. If I can access the links to the recommended website, it would be easier for me to get there.

8) CONCLUSION

"You learn more quickly under the guidance of experienced teachers. You waste a lot of time going down blind alleys if you have no one to lead you" (Maugham 2008, 34). As the first session of my MIPH program, Dr. Kabiru Gulma's coursepack material combined with Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck's video provided me an excellent learning opportunity. This course taught me the fundamentals of writing evidence-based academic paper writing and everything I needed to learn before starting my study. Also, I learned how to use Grammarly and Zotero to figure out more about the importance of citations and Turabian style to prevent plagiarism. Although English is an international language, I strived to support my study with few evidence-based claims. Overall, EUCLID has

included all the necessary information to overcome the obstacles students face while writing academic papers.

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